

Correlations between N uptake and organic N fractions (hydrolyzable and nonhydrolyzable N).^a Pantnagar, India, 1983-84 wet season.

Plant N uptake	Hydrolyzable N				Nonhydrolyzable N			
	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT	15 DT	30 DT	45 DT	60 DT
15 DT	-0.331	-	-	-	-0.116	-	-	-
30 DT	0.702**	0.500	-	-	-0.115	0.331	-	-
45 DT	0.853**	0.743**	0.594*	-	-0.175	0.321	-0.405	-
60 DT	0.870**	0.805**	0.659*	0.436	-0.051	0.339	-0.387	-0.640*
(50% flowering)								
At harvest	0.862**	0.829**	0.667**	0.468	-0.118	0.338	-0.424	-0.641*

^aSignificance at the 5% (*) and 1% (**) levels. DT = days after transplanting.

Effect of nitrogen on rice in an alkali soil

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We studied the effect of N on rice variety Damodar (CSR1) in a highly barren alkali soil without amendment during 1981-1982 wet seasons. Soil was sandy-loam with pH 10.4, 91% exchangeable Na, 0.32 meq exchangeable Ca + Mg/ 100 g, 40 kg available N/ha, 18 kg Olsen's extractable

P, and adequate K in the 0-15 cm layer.

Spacing was 15 × 15 cm with 3 seedlings/hill. N as urea was applied one-third at transplanting and the remainder as 2 equal splits at 25 and 50 d after transplanting; zinc sulfate was applied at 5.5 kg Zn/ ha. The rice was harvested 17 Nov 1981 and 16 Nov 1982.

Yield attributes and grain and straw yields significantly increased with N level (Table 1). Grain and straw N also increased significantly up to 120 kg N/ha (Table 2). Soil pH was not

organic N (6 N HCl extractable) is ultimately responsible for N in submerged soil. Hydrolyzable organic N up to 45 d after transplanting (DT) and N uptake of the rice crop at different growth stages (except N uptake at 15 DT) showed significant positive correlation (see table). The trend was reversed for nonhydrolyzable organic N except at 30 DT. □

Table 2. Influence of N level on N content of grain and straw of Darnodar grown in an alkali soil. Karnal, India, 1981-82.

N level (kg/ha)	Nitrogen content (kg/ha)			
	1981		1982	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
0	1.12	0.39	1.17	0.32
60	1.30	0.46	1.25	0.39
120	1.37	0.49	1.37	0.44
180	1.45	0.49	1.40	0.46
CD (0.05)	0.09	0.03	0.06	0.04

affected by N level, but decreased with cultivation. □

Table 1. Effect of nitrogen in an alkali soil on yield attributes and yield of Damodar (CSR1). Karnal, India, 1981-82.

N (kg/ha)	1981					1982					Soil pH after rice 1982
	Height (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		Height (cm)	Productive tillers/hill	Panicle length (cm)	Yield (t/ha)		
				Grain	Straw				Grain	Straw	
0	81.1	7.1	15.4	1.1	2.1	88.8	6.3	14.8	1.2	1.9	9.9
60	94.8	10.6	17.1	2.2	3.8	105.1	10.8	16.5	2.5	4.3	9.8
120	104.0	12.2	17.9	2.7	4.6	112.6	12.0	16.9	3.2	5.4	9.8
180	108.7	13.7	18.3	3.2	5.2	116.1	13.3	17.7	3.6	6.0	9.8
CD (0.05)	4.4	1.1	0.6	0.5	0.8	3.3	0.8	0.5	0.2	0.6	-

Consequences

Energy management in rice production

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We estimated total energy input and energy-use balance and efficiency in rice

production in relation to farm size in six randomly selected villages of Karnal district, Haryana State, north India. The farm households were categorized into five Strata on the basis of operational holding size (Cumulative Frequency Square Root method). Input-output data on the rice crop were gathered from 119 farmers (10% of the total population) representing the strata: 31

marginal (up to 1.0 ha), 26 small (1.1-2.0 ha), 29 lower medium (2.1-4.0 ha), 20 upper medium (4.1-6.0 ha), and 13 large (more than 6.0 ha).

In general, farmyard manure (FYM) and chemical fertilizers (stock resources), followed by labor and machinery (flow resources), were the most important energy inputs to rice production (Table 1). FYM and

chemical fertilizers alone accounted for about 60% of the total energy input. Energy inputs (3828 thousand kcal) were highest on the marginal farms and lowest (2287 thousand kcal) on the small farms. Grain and straw yields were highest on the large farms and lowest on the small farms.

Fertilization and manuring were the

major energy-consuming operations, followed by irrigation, plowing, and planking (Table 2). These operations collectively accounted for about 90% of the total energy input. Energy use by fertilization and manuring was about 1.6 times higher on marginal farms than on other farms. Energy use as irrigation was about double that on marginal

farms on all farm sizes except small farms.

Except for marginal farms, total and net energy output increased progressively with farm size.

The highest energy input for rice production was on marginal farms. They applied more fertilizers, but had the lowest energy output-input ratio. □

Table 1. Source of energy inputs and rice production. Haryana, India.

Farm size	Average farm size (ha)	Energy input ^d (thousand kcal/ha)							Rice production ^b (t/ha)		
		Labor		Seed	Farmyard manure	Chemical fertilizers	Machinery		Total	Grain	Straw
		Human	Bullock				Diesel engine (5 hp)	Tractor (35 hp)			
0.1-1.0	0.58	276 (7)	669 (17)	64 (2)	1675 (44)	969 (25)	175 (5)	—	3828 a	2.6 bc	4.4 bc
1.1-2.0	1.68	244 (11)	443 (20)	53 (2)	325 (14)	917 (40)	305 (13)	—	2287 c	2.4 c	4.2 c
2.1-4.0	3.00	266 (9)	529 (17)	65 (2)	824 (27)	998 (32)	392 (12)	12 (1)	3086 b	2.9 b	4.7 b
4.1-6.0	5.25	273 (8)	497 (16)	87 (3)	926 (29)	919 (29)	417 (13)	49 (2)	3168 b	3.0 b	4.7 b
6.1 & above	8.50	277 (10)	356 (12)	88 (3)	846 (29)	822 (29)	397 (14)	95 (3)	2881 b	3.6 a	6.1 a
Overall	1.46	269 (9)	468 (16)	76 (3)	848 (28)	914 (30)	376 (13)	44 (1)	2995 b	3.0 b	5.0 b

^aFigures in parentheses indicate % of total energy input. ^bIn a column, values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

Table 2. Energy use balance by operation in rice production.^a Haryana, India.

Farm size groups (ha)	Energy use (thousand kcal/ha)						Total energy input	Total energy output	Net energy output	Energy output-input ratio
	Plowing and planking	Seed, nursery raising, and transplanting	Fertilization and manuring	Irrigation	Harvesting	Threshing				
0.1-1.0	4.64 (12)	167 (4)	2844 (74)	228 (6)	63 (2)	62 (2)	3282 a	13,175 bc	10,347 b	3.4 c
1.1-2.0	371 (16)	141 (6)	1295 (57)	357 (15)	62 (3)	61 (3)	2287 c	12,573 c	10,286 b	5.5 ab
2.1-4.0	432 (14)	157 (5)	1924 (62)	448 (15)	63 (2)	62 (2)	3086 b	14,531 b	11,445 b	4.8 b
4.1-6.0	442 (14)	187 (6)	1930 (61)	478 (15)	67 (2)	64 (2)	3168 b	15,105 b	11,937 b	4.8 b
6.1 & above	392 (14)	172 (6)	1730 (60)	452 (16)	68 (2)	67 (2)	2881 b	18,373 a	15,492 a	6.4 a
Overall	417 (14)	168 (6)	1848 (62)	432 (14)	66 (2)	64 (2)	2995 b	15,462 b	12,467 b	5.2 ab

^aFigures in parentheses are % of total energy input. In a column values followed by the same letter do not differ significantly (P = 0.05) by DMRT.

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